

Preliminary Observations on ü and üe Correspondences in Southern Kurdish

Abstract

This note records a number of lexical correspondences involving Southern Kurdish ü and üe and their apparent reflexes in other Kurdish varieties, Persian, and Luri. The purpose is descriptive rather than reconstructive. No proto-form or sound law is proposed. The examples are presented as observations that may contribute to future phonological and historical analysis.

Introduction

Several lexical items in Southern Kurdish contain the vowel ü or the sequence üe. Comparison with cognate forms in Central Kurdish, Kurmanji, Persian, and Luri suggests recurring correspondences involving wê, wî, û, and î. These correspondences are not fully regular and multiple developments appear to coexist.

Selected Correspondences

Table 1. Examples involving Southern Kurdish ü

Southern Kurdish	Other Kurdish Varieties	Persian	Luri	Gloss
dür	dwêr / dûr	dûr	?	far
dünîn	dwênîn	?	?	to witness, to see, to find
xün	xwên/xwîn	xûn	xîn	blood
hür/ wîr	bîr	?	wîr	memory, recollection
hül	Hwêl/ hîl/ hûl	?	hîl	tawny, yellowish-brown, golden-brown
tûj	twêj	?	?	layer, membrane
rûtel	rûtel	?	?	poor, impoverished
tûş	tûş	-	-	Involved, afoul

Preliminary Observation

In a number of lexical correspondences, Southern Kurdish ü appears alongside:

- wê or wî in Central Kurdish and Kurmanji,
- û in Persian,
- î in Luri.

The relationship is not symmetrical. Forms containing wê or wî in Northern or Central Kurdish do not necessarily imply a Southern Kurdish ü reflex.

Examples such as:

- kwêr ~ kûr ("blind")
- gwê/gwh ~ gûş ("ear")

suggest that multiple developments coexist within Kurdish itself.

The Sequence üe

A separate pattern may involve the sequence üe.

Table 2. Examples involving Southern Kurdish üe

Southern Kurdish	Other Varieties	Gloss
düet	dot	daughter
süer	sor	red, hot, glowing
lüet	loxt (Persian)	naked, uncovered
jüer	jûr	upper/inner side
güer	gor	change
küene	Kon/kevin	old
tüem	tow/tov/toxm(Pr.)	seed
şüem	şow/şom	plowed field

Preliminary Observation

Several examples suggest that Southern Kurdish üe may correspond to o in related varieties. At present, the regularity and historical significance of this correspondence remain unclear.

Comparison with Other Developments

The reduction of üe to o may be comparable to other developments involving labial elements, including:

- **xwe** → **xo**
- **xwa** → **xa**

However, no direct historical relationship is proposed in this note.

Irregular and Ambiguous Cases

Some lexical items appear to diverge from the patterns described above. These forms may reflect additional phonological developments, lexical replacement, analogical change, borrowing, or unrelated etymologies.

Such exceptions are included intentionally, since irregular forms may be as informative as regular correspondences.

Methodological Note

This note does not argue that Southern Kurdish ü represents a separate phoneme, a labiopalatal segment, or a proto-language feature. The present goal is simply to document recurring correspondences and provide a dataset for future investigation.

Future work may examine:

- **xw/x** correspondences,
- **gw/w** correspondences,

- labialized clusters,
- k/ç/t/h correspondence networks,
- ethnonyms and culturally significant vocabulary.

Conclusion

The examples presented here suggest that Southern Kurdish *ü* and *üe* participate in a broader network of correspondences across Kurdish dialects and neighboring Iranian varieties. At present, these observations are best regarded as descriptive data rather than evidence for a specific historical reconstruction.